

Permitting and Regulatory Landscape for the Development of Cook Inlet Tidal Energy

Input to the Cook Inlet Tidal Energy Working Group

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Glossary of Abbreviations and Acronyms

ACEP	Alaska Center for Energy and Power
ACHP	Advisory Council on Historic Preservation
ADEC	Alaska Department of Environmental Conservation
ADFG	Alaska Department of Fish and Game
ADNR	Alaska Department of Natural Resources
ATEP	American Tidal Energy Project
APDES	Alaska Pollution Discharge Elimination System
AR	Allocation Round
BOEM	Bureau of Ocean Energy Management
CE	Categorical Exclusion
CfD	Contract for Difference
CFR	Code of Federal Regulations
CIRI	Cook Inlet Region, Inc.
CWA	Clean Water Act
DEH	Division of Environmental Health
DMLW	Division of Mining, Land, and Water
DOE	Department of Energy
DOG	Division of Oil and Gas
DOW	Division of Water
EA	Environmental Assessment
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EIS	Environmental Impact Statement
EFH	Essential Fish Habitat
ES	Environmental Statement
ESA	Endangered Species Act
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
FAA	Federal Aviation Administration
FONSI	Finding of No Significant Impact
FERC	Federal Energy Regulatory Commission
FWCA	Fish and Wildlife Coordination Act
GWh/yr	gigawatt hours per year
HPMP	Historic Properties Management Plan

IEA-OES	International Energy Agency-Ocean Energy Systems
IHA	Incidental Harassment Authorization
KPB	Kenai Peninsula Borough
KRC	Kenai River Center
LOA	Letter of Authorization
MDZ	Maritime Defense Zone
MMPA	Marine Mammal Protection Act
MOA	Memorandum of Agreement
MRE	Marine Renewable Energy
MW	megawatts
MWh	megawatts per hour
NEPA	National Environmental Policy Act
NHPA	National Historic Properties Act
NMFS	National Marine Fisheries Service
NOI	Notice of Intent
NWP-5	Nationwide Permit 5
NWP-52	Nationwide Permit 52
NY	New York
OHA	Office of History and Archaeology
OPMP	Office of Project Management and Permitting
ORPC	Ocean Renewable Power Systems
PA	Programmatic Agreement
PATON	Private Aids to Navigation
PCN	Pre-Construction Notification
PEA	Programmatic Environmental Assessment
PEIS	Programmatic Environmental Impact Statement
RCA	Regulatory Commission of Alaska
RITE	Roosevelt Island Tidal Energy Project
ROD	Record of Decision
R-STEP	Renewable Energy Siting through Technical Engagement Planning
SHPO	State Historic Preservation Office
SWPPP	Stormwater Pollution Prevention Plan
TWh	terawatt hour
WOTUS	Waters of the United States

WPTO	Water Power Technologies Office
UK	United Kingdom
USACE	U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
USCBP	U.S. Customs and Border Protection
USCG	U.S. Coast Guard
USFWS	U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service

Executive Summary

Introduction

Cook Inlet, recognized as the most important tidal energy resource in the nation, holds approximately one-third of the United States' technically recoverable tidal energy resources.¹ Its immediate proximity to Alaska's primary electricity grid – the Alaska Railbelt – which serves 65% of the state's population, makes it an ideal candidate for tidal energy development.

In 2022, with funding from the State of Alaska, the Alaska Center for Energy and Power (ACEP) at the University of Alaska Fairbanks formed the *Cook Inlet Tidal Energy Working Group*. The working group sought to characterize and discuss the opportunities for harnessing tidal energy from Cook Inlet and was composed of tidal energy leaders; federal agencies and regulators; state and local regulatory agencies; local utilities; tidal energy scientists from Alaska universities and national labs; as well as local consultants and non-profit organizations. The working group proposed an aggressive goal: to install 100 megawatts (MW) of tidal energy capacity by 2035. Achieving this goal would require rapid increases in investments in tidal energy demonstration projects. Six working group meetings were held from December 2022 through May 2023 with the objective of discussing and documenting concerns, challenges, and opportunities in the areas of data needs and gaps, permitting and regulatory challenges, resource assessments, and cost projections. ACEP intends to issue summary reports on all working group topic areas. However, due to the time-sensitive nature of this content, this Permitting and Regulatory Landscape report has been issued in advance to coincide with current state agency discussions.

Permitting and Regulatory Landscape

This Permitting and Regulatory Landscape Report intends to highlight the authorizations and processes required to develop tidal energy projects in Cook Inlet. The goal of this report is to support knowledge and information-sharing while providing context, recommendations, and opportunities for permitting and regulatory processes. This report explores the regulatory and permitting landscape for tidal energy in Cook Inlet and can serve as a reference in energy planning and legislation development. Key aspects include:

- **Regulatory Framework:** The process of obtaining permits, authorizations, and licenses for tidal energy infrastructure installations in Cook Inlet will involve extensive coordination with a variety of government regulatory agencies and stakeholders. Understanding how these regulations interact is vital for project advancement.
- **Permitting Process:** The permitting process can be broadly divided into two main categories: “Grid-Connected” and “Non-Grid Connected” installations, each offering several pathways depending on the project specifics such as type, size, and intent of the proposed device(s) and location and duration of deployment. To meet the working group goal of 100 MW of tidal energy by 2035, permitting efforts are likely to include multiple pathways under both categories occurring concurrently.
- **State-Level Coordination:** Within Alaska waters, project developers will need to navigate a detailed set of state and local regulations, policies, and procedures. A major infrastructure project may require coordination with upwards of ten state regulatory divisions positioned within three departments. Additionally, the project's potential cable routes and onshore infrastructure may cross a myriad of surface landowners within the Kenai Peninsula Borough (KPB), including private landowners, state and federal agencies, Alaska Native Corporations, or village corporations. Importantly, and justifiably, each of these entities has its own

¹Kilcher, Levi, Michelle Fogarty, and Michael Lawson. 2021. Marine Energy in the United States: An Overview of Opportunities. Golden, CO: National Renewable Energy Laboratory. NREL/TP-5700-78773. <https://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy21osti/78773.pdf>.

objectives and missions, which may align with or oppose the swift development of tidal energy.

- **Strategic Collaboration:** Regardless of installation type, permitting tidal energy infrastructure will involve many of the key regulatory agencies and stakeholders and necessitate compliance with the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA)², underscoring the importance of a collaborative and strategic approach to permitting. This approach is essential to reduce cost, avoid duplicated efforts and project delays, and effectively manage agency workloads.

Path Forward

Whereas this document was intended to explore tidal energy within Cook Inlet, key processes and recommendations described in this document can be applied to other offshore- and land-based renewable technologies and energy infrastructure development in other parts of Alaska. Understanding the intricate network of regulatory and permitting requirements, along with their interactions, overlaps, and occasional conflicts, is essential for the success of renewable energy development in Alaska. This document highlights key areas that can accelerate the commercialization of tidal energy in Cook Inlet, fostering innovation and potentially expanding tidal energy deployments across Alaska. A complete list of recommendations for the State of Alaska and/or project developers is detailed in Section 7.0 and summarized below:

- Promote collaborative state and federal permitting processes through programs such as the Office of Project Management and Permitting (OPMP).
- Use a flexible and responsible management approach for project permitting to accommodate evolving project needs and insights.
- Initiate a comprehensive state-funded assessment to gather and process information pertinent to tidal energy development in Cook Inlet, culminating in a published report that will act as a central resource for all relevant stakeholders.
- Consider offering state funding support to meet the obligatory cost-sharing stipulations commonly associated with Federal grants, aimed specifically at supporting projects and innovations within Alaska.
- Establish a state-directed collaborative to apply for the Department of Energy (DOE) Renewable Energy Siting through Technical Engagement Planning (R-STEP) program.
- Consider state-level legislation and/or revenue mechanisms to enable the development of tidal energy in Cook Inlet and potentially across Alaska.

² NEPA compliance is required for all activities authorized by federal permits or supported by federal funds.

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1 Introduction

Cook Inlet is the most important tidal energy resource in the United States, containing approximately one-third of the country’s theoretically and technically recoverable tidal energy resources. Extending to Anchorage, Cook Inlet offers immediate proximity to the state’s primary transmission corridor, the Railbelt, which supplies electricity to 65% of Alaska’s population.³ Currently, fossil fuels generate approximately 80% of the Railbelt’s power, which the Alaska Department of Natural Resources (ADNR) forecasts will no longer meet local demand by 2027.⁴

Tidal energy resources can be quantified as theoretical, technical, or practical. The theoretical potential of Cook Inlet, which assumes idealized technology and unlimited deployment, is estimated at 160,000 terawatt hours (TWh) per year⁵. However, considering the limitations of current technologies and practical deployment limits, the technically recoverable energy is estimated at 80,000 TWh annually⁶. This amount represents a substantial 15-fold increase over the Railbelt’s electricity consumption of approximately 5.2 TWh per year^{7,8}. The immense potential of Cook Inlet’s tidal power has been recognized for decades, but it is only within the past twenty years that dam-free technologies for capturing this energy have been developed and tested. This advancement offers significant opportunities for Alaska and energy developers to leverage the substantial tidal forces of Cook Inlet to meet the Railbelt electricity demand. Additionally, the surplus energy generated could be used in the production of hydrogen or other valuable commodities. The development of tidal energy in Cook Inlet promises to enhance Alaska’s energy system by leveraging local resources to bolster resilience, independence, and security, while positioning Alaska as a global leader in tidal energy innovation.

To harness Cook Inlet’s significant energy resource, regulators and tidal energy developers must consider the economic, cultural, and environmental context of the region. Encircling Alaska’s most densely populated area, Cook Inlet provides critical access to the Port of Alaska, a vital hub processing approximately half of the state’s inbound cargo. Located within Cook Inlet Region, Inc. (CIRI) lands, the inlet is not only a center of geological activity, marked by active volcanoes and oil and gas platforms, but also a region rich in cultural heritage. It is home to five federally recognized Alaska Native tribes and several protected areas including national parks and wildlife refuges. Its waters are teeming with life, supporting seven marine mammal species – including the endangered beluga whale, Steller sea lion, and northern sea otter – and a diverse fish population that includes salmon, herring, smelt, cod, sablefish, rockfish, and halibut. These fisheries are a cornerstone of local commerce, subsistence, and recreation, deeply woven into the state’s economic and cultural identity. Moreover, Cook Inlet presents formidable operational challenges – including fast currents, extreme and abrasive sediment loads, constantly shifting seabed, and severe icing in the winter – creating a particularly harsh environment for deploying and maintaining offshore energy infrastructure. Despite these challenges, the complex and dynamic environment of Cook Inlet represents an ideal location for advancing tidal

³ Renewable Portfolio Standard Assessment for Alaska’s Railbelt | NREL

⁴ State of Alaska, Department of Natural Resources, Division of Oil and Gas [2022-cook-inlet-gas-forecast-report.pdf](#)

⁵ Haas et al., Assessment of Energy Production Potential from Tidal Streams in the United States (Georgia Tech Research Corporation 2011).

⁶ Kilcher, Levi, Michelle Fogarty, and Michael Lawson. 2021. Marine Energy in the United States: An Overview of Opportunities. Golden, CO: National Renewable Energy Laboratory. NREL/TP-5700-78773. <https://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy21osti/78773.pdf>.

⁷ U.S. Energy Information Administration. 2023. “Alaska State Energy Profile.” Accessed May 25, 2023. <https://www.eia.gov/state/print.php?sid=AK>.

⁸ Readers are encouraged to review Schwarz, Marty, Ben McGilton, Levi Kilcher, Kelly Gjestvang, and Greg Stark. 2024. Evaluating the Impact of Tidal Energy in the Cook Inlet on Alaska’s Railbelt Electrical Grid. Golden, CO: National Renewable Energy Laboratory. NREL/TP-5700-85943. <https://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy24osti/85943.pdf>.

energy. The premise is that if tidal energy can economically be produced in Cook Inlet in an environmentally safe manner, it could theoretically be successful anywhere in the country.

This Permitting and Regulatory Landscape Report intends to highlight the key authorizations and processes required for the installation of a tidal energy device(s) and/or any associated monitoring equipment in Cook Inlet. The goal of this report is to support knowledge and information sharing while providing context, recommendations, and opportunities for permitting and regulatory processes.

2 Key Regulatory Agencies

The strongest currents in Cook Inlet are found within a natural restriction formed by two opposing peninsulas, the East and West Forelands, see Figure 1. This area, also known as Upper Cook Inlet, is located within state waters and has been the primary focus for tidal development due to its renowned currents and proximity to existing infrastructure. It represents the most populated watershed in Alaska, with shoreline bordered by the Municipality of Anchorage, Kenai Peninsula Borough, and Matanuska-Susitna Borough.

Figure 1: Upper Cook Inlet Vicinity Map

Permitting and regulatory requirements for each phase of tidal development in Cook Inlet (i.e. feasibility, testing, construction, operation, etc.) may vary widely; however, key agencies likely to be involved are provided in Figure 2. Note this list is not intended to be exhaustive nor represent every potential tidal development project. Alaska-based construction, specifically within the dynamic Cook Inlet waters, presents myriad operational and logistical hurdles that each require their own permitting and regulatory review. Moreover, this report is focused on tidal development in Upper Cook Inlet, which is located within state waters. For projects located within federal waters, developers must also engage with the Bureau of Ocean Energy Management (BOEM). The intricate network of activities, diverse

wildlife, and overlapping jurisdictions within Upper Cook Inlet requires continuous and effective collaboration with various regulatory agencies at the federal, state, and local level.

FEDERAL				LOCAL	
FERC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federal Power Act • Energy Policy Act 	USACE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rivers and Harbors Act Section 10 • Clean Water Act Section 404 	NMFS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Endangered Species Act • Marine Mammal Protection Act (MMPA) • Magnuson-Stevens Act 	USFWS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ESA/MMPA • Fish and Wildlife Coordination Act • Migratory Bird Treaty Act 	KPB/KRC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-Agency Permit • Floodplain Permit • Vegetation Management 	
EPA <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clean Water Act • Spill Prevention, Control, and Countermeasure Rule 	FAA <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determination of No Hazard to Air Navigation 	USCBP <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jones Act (Merchant Marine Act of 1920) 	USCG <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Notice to Mariners • Movement Regulations • Private Aids to Navigation 	Native Corporations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land Use Authorization • Letter of Non-Objection 	
STATE					
ADNR, DMLW/DOG <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land Use Authorization • Right of Way/Easement • Tidelands Lease 	ADNR, SHPO <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Historic Preservation Act 	ADFG <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Title 16, Fish Habitat • Public Safety • Title 5, Special Area Permit 	ADEC, DOW <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clean Water Act • Section 401 Certification • APDES/NPDES 	ADEC, DEH <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domestic waste • Drinking water 	

Figure 2: Agencies that may be involved in permitting Upper Cook Inlet tidal energy devices and projects.

3 National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA)

The development of tidal energy in Cook Inlet, including any early research, data collection, or feasibility studies, will require compliance with the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA). Under NEPA, federal agencies must evaluate the environmental impacts of their proposed activities prior to decision-making. The NEPA process is triggered by activities that either (1) occur within federal lands/waters, (2) require the issuance of a federal permit, or (3) use federal funds. Because the Upper Cook Inlet is located within state waters, compliance with the NEPA process would likely be initiated by the issuance of a federal permit, preliminary license, or distribution of federal funds. This report aims to describe the general NEPA process as it applies to Cook Inlet tidal development. Additional information regarding NEPA can be found within the *Citizen’s Guide to NEPA* on the Council on Environmental Quality (CEQ) website: <https://ceq.doe.gov/>.

3.1 Lead Agency and Consultations

Under NEPA, a designated lead agency oversees the preparation of environmental analyses and documentation to ensure compliance with the Act. In scenarios involving multiple federal agencies, which is likely to be the case in Cook Inlet tidal development, the lead agency is selected based on expertise, regulatory authority, and capacity to manage the process effectively. This role is essential for orchestrating the environmental review process and guaranteeing comprehensive consideration of all environmental impacts. The lead agency must consult other agencies, governments, and private persons when their involvement is reasonably foreseeable. For the development of tidal energy in Cook Inlet, the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (USACE), Federal Energy Regulatory Commission (FERC), or Department of Energy (DOE) are likely candidates to assume the lead role in the NEPA process. It is crucial to identify and engage the project’s lead agency early in the process to ensure compliance with NEPA and meet project timelines. Consultations and corresponding authorizations likely to be required for tidal energy activities in Cook Inlet are detailed in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Consultations and corresponding authorizations likely to be required during the NEPA process.

The NEPA process requires a collaborative approach involving multiple federal and state agencies. These agencies will likely request further details from the developer to facilitate their environmental review, including, but not limited to, archeological/cultural assessments and acoustic impact studies. Considering the expenses, logistical demands, and time required for data gathering and analysis within the confined geographic area of Cook Inlet, adopting a cooperative and preemptive strategy could prove beneficial and is discussed further in Section 7.0.

3.2 NEPA Assessment Levels

There are three levels of analysis a lead agency may use under NEPA: Categorical Exclusion (CE), Environmental Assessment (EA), and Environmental Impact Statement (EIS). Key decisions for determining which level of analysis required are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Overview of the NEPA Process.

3.2.1 Categorical Exclusions

The most expedited process under NEPA is the application of a CE, as outlined in Appendix B to Subpart D of 10 Code of Federal Regulations (CFR) Part 1021. Each federal agency has its own specific CEs. However, should the lead agency lack a CE for a proposed project, it can adopt one from another federal agency. This adoption must adhere to the adopting agency's guidelines, which typically involve confirming the CE's relevance, soliciting public feedback, and formally documenting the adoption. Documentation must include a determination that the proposed action is substantially the same as those covered by the original CE and that no extraordinary circumstances exist that would require a more detailed EA or EIS. This process was recently streamlined under the Fiscal Responsibility Act of 2023 and represents a significant opportunity for tidal development permitting in Cook Inlet.

Notably, the DOE's CE B5.25, which pertains to small-scale renewable energy research, development, and pilot

projects in aquatic environments, is accessible to developers.⁹ However, its use is designated for temporary installations and is prohibited within areas of high biological sensitivity without explicit permission from the lead agency. While CE B5.25 could potentially apply to initial tidal development efforts in Cook Inlet, its use is limited and contingent upon approval from the project's lead agency and consultation with National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS) and U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS). It is important to note that no CE exists that fully supports large-scale tidal energy projects; to meet the ambitious goal of generating 10 MW of tidal energy by 2035, an EA or EIS would be required.

3.2.2 Environmental Assessment

An EA is a concise document that includes the purpose and need of the proposal, proposed alternatives, and a brief review of the environmental impacts. The assessment culminates in either a Finding of No Significant Impact (FONSI), which indicates minimal environmental consequences, or, if substantial environmental impacts are anticipated, the initiation of an EIS. Under the Fiscal Responsibility Act of 2023, the EA process must be completed within a one-year timeframe, starting from the date the agency decides to undertake an EA and concluding with the publication of an EA/FONSI.

3.2.3 Environmental Impact Statement

Federal agencies prepare an Environmental Impact Statement (EIS) if the environmental impacts of a proposed action are likely to be significant. The EIS process includes several key steps: the issuance of a Notice of Intent (NOI) to prepare an EIS, releasing a Draft EIS for public comment, finalizing a Record of Decision (ROD), and making a final agency decision. An EIS is more detailed than an EA and includes a thorough examination of viable alternatives and evaluates the cumulative effects of the proposed action in conjunction with all other current and anticipated developments within the project's vicinity. In areas like Cook Inlet, where there is a convergence of oil and gas exploration, commercial fishing, tourism, and maritime industries, distinguishing between an EA and EIS is crucial. According to the Fiscal Responsibility Act of 2023, the EIS must be completed within a two-year timeframe, starting from the release of the NOI to the signing of the ROD. Typically, the groundwork for an EIS is set into motion well before the NOI is published. This early phase requires extensive preparation and could result in a timeline for the developers that exceeds two years.

⁹ <https://www.energy.gov/nepa/articles/10-cfr-1021-national-environmental-policy-act-implementing-procedures-doe-2024> [Accessed 8/2024]

4 Permitting Categories and Pathways

Federal permits required for tidal energy development in Cook Inlet can be broadly divided into two categories: “Grid-Connected Installations” and “Non-Grid Connected Installations.” Both categories allow for multiple permitting pathways depending on the type, size, location, and intent of the proposed device(s). Figure 5 provides a simplified overview of the two categories and their associated permitting pathways, displaying a gradient of increasing time and cost as the complexity of the permitted work increases. The *Marine Energy Environmental Toolkit for Permitting and Licensing* is an additional tool for project developers to access, review, and compile relevant regulation, information, and available literature.¹⁰ To achieve the goal of 100 MW of tidal energy by 2035, permitting efforts are likely to include multiple pathways under both categories occurring simultaneously. These pathways share many of the key regulatory agencies and will each require evaluation under NEPA, making the need for a collaborative and thoughtful permitting approach critical to reduce cost, avoid duplicated efforts and project delays, and minimize agency workloads.

Figure 5: Theoretical State-Water Permitting Pathways.

4.1 Non-Grid Connected Installations

Although located in state waters, Upper Cook Inlet is a navigable Water of the United States (WOTUS) under the Clean Water Act (CWA), requiring USACE engagement and permitting under Section 10 of the Rivers and Harbors Act. USACE typically serves as the lead agency for NEPA permitting for any non-grid connected projects in state waters within Cook Inlet. However, as discussed in Section 3.1, the lead agency may vary based on the type and funding associated with a particular project.

Regardless of lead agency, the classification of Cook Inlet as a navigable WOTUS requires USACE permitting and authorization for most tidal energy development activities. USACE authorizations likely to be applicable to tidal development in Cook Inlet include Nationwide Permit 5 (NWP 5), Nationwide Permit 52 (NWP 52), and Individual Permits.

¹⁰ <https://marineenergy.app>.

4.1.1 Nationwide Permit 5

The collection of baseline resource assessment data (i.e. velocity, turbidity, turbulence, ice floes, etc.) is critical for developers to assess, scope, and establish the feasibility of a project. In general, the use of monitoring equipment is eligible for the USACE NWP 5: Scientific Monitoring Devices. In many areas of the U.S., NWPs can significantly streamline federal permitting efforts; however, because Cook Inlet is critical habitat for select endangered species, the environmental impact of this type of data collection should not be underestimated. Nationwide Permit General Condition 18 stipulates “...no activity is authorized under any NWP which ‘may affect’ a listed species or critical habitat, unless ESA section 7 consultation addressing the consequences of the proposed activity on the listed species or critical habitat has been completed.” In Cook Inlet, the use of certain scientific monitoring devices¹¹ or deployment methods¹² may trigger additional authorizations and/or mitigation measures under NMFS and USFWS. Non-federal permittees must submit a pre-construction notification (PCN) to USACE and consult with NMFS and USFWS to ensure compliance with the requirements of the ESA. Federal permittees must follow their internal procedures for consultation under NEPA. This added layer of complexity demonstrates the finer intricacies of Cook Inlet permitting and the need for experienced permittees in order to avoid lengthy and potentially costly delays.

4.1.2 Nationwide Permit 52

Non-grid connected projects in state waters that are “experimental” and used “to collect information on their performance and environmental effects” can benefit from the use of NWP 52: Water-Based Renewable Energy. NWP 52 is a relatively new permit, that includes the construction, expansion, modification, or removal of water-based wind, water-based solar, wave energy, or hydrokinetic renewable energy generation pilot projects and their attendant features. Notably, attendant features include land-based collection and distribution facilities, control facilities, roads, parking lots, and stormwater management facilities. NWP 52 is likely to be a useful permitting mechanism in Cook Inlet to quickly begin testing tidal devices, however, structures authorized under NWP 52 must be removed at project completion unless they are authorized by a separate USACE authorization. As with NWP 5, NWP 52 would require consultation with NMFS and USFWS.

4.1.3 Individual Permit

Long-term tidal device installation for consumption by an end-user and not connected to a utility (interstate) grid, or the conversion of a pilot project to a long-term non-grid connected installation, would require authorization under a traditional USACE Individual Permit. Individual permits differ from NWPs in that they require a full public interest review of an individual application. The public notice, usually lasting 30 days, is distributed to all known interested stakeholders and guides the permit decision. The Individual Permit process requires a full NEPA review for the proposed project and consultation with other federal and state agencies. Under EPA’s CWA 404(b)(1) Guidelines, USACE may only permit the least environmentally damaging practicable alternative proposed by the applicant, making the consultation and mitigation negotiations critical for permit issuance and project success. Early stakeholder engagement may be crucial to establish practicable alternatives that can garner public support.

4.2 Grid-Connected Installations

Any grid-connected project will require coordination and permitting through FERC who will serve as the lead-agency for the NEPA process. The required authorizations and timeline for receiving authorization under FERC will differ based on project scope and may include the Verdant Order, Pilot License, or Traditional License. Importantly, grid-connected tidal energy research and development in Cook Inlet, a navigable WOTUS, is likely to still require permitting and authorization under USACE in addition to FERC licensing.

¹¹ For example, the auditory range of marine mammals can span 10 Hz to 200 kHz. Instruments operating within this range require more detailed review during permitting.

¹² Some examples: Buoy lines may present entanglement risk. Surface presence may impact navigation. Vessel operations for deployment and retrieval will need marine life avoidance procedures.

4.2.1 Verdant Order

For short-duration, small-scale projects within state waters that connect to the utility grid but do not displace power from the grid, the FERC Verdant Order is an important viable path to encourage initial tidal energy device deployments within Cook Inlet. As succinctly summarized by Stoel Rives LLP in 2008, “Under the 2005 ‘Verdant Order,’ a developer does not need a FERC license for a project if (a) it is testing an experimental technology for a short period of time for the purpose of conducting studies and (b) any power generated from the test facility is not transmitted into, and does not displace power from, the national energy grid. These test projects must still obtain other federal and state approvals, as necessary, such as CWA Section 404 discharge permits, Section 401 water quality certifications, and Endangered Species Act (“ESA”) Section 7 consultations, among others.”¹³ It should be noted that these projects may connect to the utility grid as required for the individual technology to function. However, precautions at the point of electrical interconnection must be included to ensure that no electrical energy flows into the grid and instead flows entirely to an end-user or other load bank.

4.2.2 Pilot License

For grid-connected, utility-scale (< 5 MW) projects within State of Alaska waters that are intended to be deployed for shorter durations (nominally five years with the ability to request up to 10 years), the FERC Pilot Project License process is appropriate and is an important option to pursue to advance the goals of tidal energy deployments in the Cook Inlet. While this FERC Pilot Project License process generally follows the traditional NEPA permitting process described in the Traditional License section below, the limited size and duration of the proposed project results in the commensurate reduction in time and cost for the three application stages and generally results in less onerous license requirements regarding environmental monitoring, et al. Further, the results of a successful tidal energy project operated under a Pilot Project License can be used for the subsequent submission of a traditional FERC license application. As such, the project developer can defer the time and cost of a traditional license over a longer period of time while increasing regulator and stakeholder confidence by successfully executing a smaller project within the Pilot Project License framework.

4.2.3 Traditional License

For grid-connected, utility-scale (> 5 MW) projects within State of Alaska waters to proceed, developers must follow the traditional NEPA permitting process. The Traditional License process consists of three application “stages” that require different amounts and kinds of information at each stage. The first stage, known as the Preliminary License Application¹⁴, reserves an area for future development to allow developers to perform site characterization and collect baseline data. Developers should engage with appropriate agencies before the Preliminary License Application is submitted. Following this stage, developers move to the Draft License Application stage and then to the Final License Application. Developers must include draft proposals for environmental and recreational monitoring plans, safeguard plans, inspection and maintenance plans, and fuel and hazardous substance plans, among others, in their Draft License Application. Following agency and stakeholder commenting periods and subsequent negotiations, the developer submits the Final License Application to FERC. From the filing of the first stage Preliminary License Application to the issuance of a FERC License is a multi-year process.

¹³ <https://www.stoel.com/ferc-licensing-process-for-in-stream-hydrokinetic-projects> [Accessed 8/2023]

¹⁴ There are currently three preliminary licenses for tidal energy in Cook Inlet: P-15109 (Tidal Energy Corporation), P-15110 (Littoral Power Systems), and P-15166 (ORPC)

5 State and Local Permitting

The State of Alaska's environmental permitting process is a comprehensive system involving multiple departments and divisions, each with specific roles and responsibilities to ensure the conservation, improvement, and protection of Alaska's natural resources and environment. This multi-layered approach to environmental permitting ensures infrastructure development is carried out responsibly, with due consideration for the state's unique environmental and social contexts. A brief overview of state agencies, divisions, and offices that may be involved in a major Cook Inlet tidal development project are highlighted below.

5.1 Alaska Department of Environmental Conservation¹⁵

The Alaska Department of Environmental Conservation (ADEC) is dedicated to conserving, improving, and protecting Alaska's natural resources and environment. Its mission is to enhance the health, safety, economic, and social well-being of Alaskans. The following Divisions within the ADEC have been identified as being potentially involved in a major Cook Inlet Tidal Development project:

- **Division of Water (DOW):** ADEC-DOW manages the Alaska Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (APDES) permits for discharges to surface waters, domestic, municipal, and industrial wastewater, stormwater, and small suction dredge operations. Project developers could be regulated under ADEC-DOW for activities including, but not limited to, horizontal directional drilling, section 401 certifications, storm water pollution prevention plans (SWPPP), and excavation dewatering.
- **Division of Air Quality (AQ):** ADEC-AQ regulates air emissions and provides air quality permits to ensure compliance with state and federal standards. Project developers could be regulated under this agency for activities including, but not limited to, changes to existing permitted sources, installation of emission sources, and the construction of buildings that will hold future emission sources.
- **Division of Environmental Health (EH):** ADEC-EH focuses on the environmental health aspects, including the safety of food and drinking water. Project developers could be regulated under this agency for activities including, but not limited to, the installation of a temporary or permanent camp, construction of a sanitary waste management system, and installation of a drinking water source for project personnel.
- **Spill Prevention and Response Division (SPAR):** ADEC-SPAR ensures facilities have adequate spill prevention and response plans for oil and hazardous substances. Project developers could be regulated under this agency for activities including, but not limited to, the bulk storage of oil or hazardous substances or onshore construction through or near an existing contaminated site.

5.2 Alaska Department of Natural Resources¹⁶

The Alaska Department of Natural Resources (DNR) has a multifaceted mission to develop, conserve, and maximize the use of Alaska's natural resources in the public interest. It manages state-owned land, water, and natural resources, excluding fish and game, and is organized into several divisions, each with specific responsibilities.

Notably, the **Office of Project Management and Permitting (OPMP)** supports private industry, regulators, and the public by leading multi-agency permit coordination. Project developers have access to this program, which is designed to synchronize project timelines with statutory, regulatory, and various permitting processes as closely as possible, in accordance with project objectives and milestones. Additional divisions within the DNR that may be involved with a major Cook Inlet tidal energy project are briefly summarized below.

- **Division of Mining, Land, and Water (DMLW):** ADNR-DMLW manages state land holdings and

¹⁵ <https://dec.alaska.gov/>

¹⁶ <https://dnr.alaska.gov/>

resources, including mineral (excluding oil and gas) and water resources. Work within the state waters of Upper Cook Inlet will require authorization under ADNR-DMLW. Additionally, project developers could be regulated under this agency for other activities such as excavation dewatering.

- **Division of Oil and Gas (DOG):** ADNR-DOG develops and manages oil and gas leasing programs and oversees pipeline systems. Project developers could be regulated under this agency if they are an oil and gas developer operating within an existing oil and gas lease or if they are a project developer using existing infrastructure regulated by the ADNR-DOG. Notably, Upper Cook Inlet contains seventeen oil and gas platforms and multiple pipelines. Development of Cook Inlet tidal energy is likely to intersect with the local oil and gas industry, presenting an interesting overlap in potential jurisdictions for ADNR-DMLW and ADNR-DOG.
- **Division of Parks and Outdoor Recreation:** The Division of Parks and Outdoor Recreation manages state parks and recreational programs. Project developers could be regulated under this agency if they overlap with any of the state parks or recreational programs in Cook Inlet.
- **Office of History and Archeology (OHA):** OHA is dedicated to preserving and interpreting Alaska's past and serves as Alaska's State Historic Preservation Office (SHPO) pursuant to the National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA) of 1966. A Section 106 review, mandated by NHPA, requires federal agencies to consider the impact of their projects on historic sites. This review is administered by the ADNR-OHA.

5.3 Alaska Department of Fish and Game¹⁷

The Alaska Department of Fish and Game (ADFG) is dedicated to protecting, maintaining, and improving the state's fish, game, and aquatic plant resources. Their mission encompasses managing these resources in a way that benefits the economy and the well-being of Alaskans, adhering to the principle of sustainability. The following divisions and sections within ADFG have been identified as being potentially involved with a major Cook Inlet tidal energy development project.

- **Habitat Section:** The Habitat Section maintains sustainable fish and wildlife populations and has a statutory responsibility to protect freshwater habitat and ensure free passage for anadromous fish¹⁸. Project developers could be regulated under this agency for activities including, but not limited to, installation within anadromous waters or work within designated state refuges, critical habitat areas, and sanctuaries known collectively as Special Areas.
- **Division of Wildlife Conservation:** This division maintains and enhances opportunities to hunt, trap, and view wildlife. They also issue State Public Safety Permits which are required before a person can kill, destroy, relocate, or haze wild animals creating a nuisance or a threat to public safety. At minimum, project developers should consider collaboration with this Division to obtain a Public Safety Permit when undertaking tasks that could pose a wildlife-related hazard to worker safety.
- **Division of Sport Fisheries:** The Division of Sport Fisheries manages fish hatcheries and oversees the state's aquatic resource permit program. Project developers could be regulated under this agency for any activity within a sport fishery.
- **Division of Commercial Fisheries:** This division manages commercial, subsistence, and personal use fisheries within the jurisdiction of the State of Alaska. Project developers could be regulated under this agency for any activity within a commercial fishery.

5.4 Regulatory Commission of Alaska¹⁹

The Regulatory Commission of Alaska (RCA) plays a crucial role in overseeing public utilities within the state. Its primary purpose is to certify qualified providers of public utility and pipeline services, ensuring that these services are safe, adequate, and available at just and reasonable rates, terms, and conditions. Whereas the RCA works directly with

¹⁷ <https://www.adfg.alaska.gov/>

¹⁸ Cook Inlet anadromous species include pacific salmon (chinook, sockeye, coho, pink, and chum), steelhead, and dolly varden.

¹⁹ <https://rca.alaska.gov/RCAWeb/Home.aspx>

local utilities, the RCA's statutes and regulations on energy conservation and net metering standards could provide the framework for monitoring ongoing tidal operations to include reporting, inspections, and audits.

5.5 Local Agencies/Stakeholders

The Kenai Peninsula Borough (KPB)²⁰ encompasses areas on both the east and west sides of Cook Inlet and holds regulatory authority over infrastructure projects through its Code of Ordinances and permit process. For example, development projects within the Habitat Protection District or adjacent to water bodies may require a Kenai River Center (KRC)²¹ Multi-Agency Permit. The Borough's ordinances are categorized by topic, with each category providing detailed regulations that could impact infrastructure projects. Therefore, it is crucial for project planners to engage with the KRC early on to ensure adherence to all relevant regulations and to secure the required permits before starting any construction activities.

Additionally, infrastructure associated with the project, encompassing both land-based and maritime components, has the potential to extend across various properties and easements. This could require coordination with the existing network of utility cables and pipelines, potentially requiring non-objection certificates or new surface use agreements.

6 Permitting Strategies

Undoubtedly, the regulatory processes at the federal, state, and local level are complex and require careful coordination. Developers, regulators, and policy makers can facilitate a streamlined permitting process for Cook Inlet tidal energy development using one or more proven permitting strategies as described below.

6.1 Stakeholder Engagement

The development of a tidal energy project in Cook Inlet is likely to involve a diverse range of landowners and stakeholders, including private individuals, state and federal entities, Alaska Native Corporations, and village corporations. Notably, the impact Cook Inlet tidal development would have on the Railbelt and Alaskan economy lends itself to an expansive and diverse set of stakeholders. The initial list of stakeholders identified by the working group included over ninety stakeholders, listed in Figure 6, spanning across various industries, agencies, and communities, emphasizing the need for proactive, sustained, and consistent outreach and messaging.

Engaging with stakeholder groups across a variety of sectors is essential to ensure communities' and stakeholders' needs and concerns are addressed throughout the project lifetime. Opportunities for public engagement are embedded within NEPA and many of the regulatory agency processes. For any permitting effort, it is crucial to engage with agencies before submitting applications and to continue this engagement throughout the application process. If permits are successfully issued, engagement continues before and during project deployment, execution, and decommissioning. Given the duration and complexity of engagement, a unified stakeholder outreach program for Cook Inlet tidal energy, to include the hosting and maintenance of a database of relevant stakeholders and agencies, could significantly improve the success of individual project developers.

²⁰ <https://www.kpb.us/>

²¹ <https://www.kpb.us/river-center>

<p>Federal Agencies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federal Energy Regulatory Commission • US Army Corps of Engineers • Environmental Protection Agency • Federal Aviation Administration • National Marine Fisheries Service • US Customs and Border Protection • US Coast Guard • US Fish and Wildlife Service 	<p>Alaska Native Corporations & Tribes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bristol Bay Native Corporation • Chickaloon Village • Chugach Corporation • Cook Inlet Region, Inc. (CIRI) • Doyon, Ltd. • Eklutna Village • Kenaitze Village • Knik Village • Koniaq, Inc. • Native Village of Port Graham • Native Village of Nanwalek • Ninilchik Village Tribe • Tyonek Village • Salamatof Native Association • Seldivia Village 	<p>Subsistence & Recreational</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Air/Water Pilots • Clamming • Fishing / Hunting • Kenai Peninsula Fishermen's Association • Kite/Boretide Surfing • Powered Paragliding • Private Marinas • Recreational Boating • Upper Cook Inlet Drift Association • Wildlife Viewing 	<p>Defense</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear Space Force Station • Eielson Air Force Base • Fort Greely • Fort Wainwright • Joint Base Elmendorf Richardson (JBER) • US Coast Guard – Pacific Area
<p>State & Local Agencies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ADEC Division of Air Quality • ADEC Division of Environmental Health • ADEC Division of Spill Prevention and Response • ADEC Division of Water • Alaska Dept of Fish & Game • ADNR Division of Mining, Land, and Water • ADNR Division of Oil & Gas • ADNR State Historic Preservation Office • Alaska Governor's Office • Kenai Peninsula Borough • Kenai River Center • Regulatory Commission of Alaska 	<p>Oil & Gas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AK Oil & Gas Association • Alaska Gasline Development Corp. • Blue Crest Energy, Inc. • Cook Inlet Energy, LLC • Furie Operating Alaska, LLC • Hilcorp Alaska, LLC 	<p>Utilities & End Users</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chugach Electric Assoc. • General Public • Golden Valley Electric Assoc. • Homer Electric Assoc. • Matanuska Electric Assoc. • Railbelt Reliability Council • Railbelt Regional Coordination • Seward Electric System 	<p>Shipping & Tourism</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cruise Lines • Fishing Charters • Local Docks • Ocean Visitors Center • OSK Systems Marine Dock • Port of Alaska • Rig Tenders Dock
<p>Government Funded Groups</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alaska Energy Authority • AK Energy Security Task Force • AK Office of Energy Innovation • AK Hydrogen Working Group • Cook Inlet Beluga Whale Recovery Implementation Task Force • Cook Inlet Tidal Working Group • National Renewable Energy Laboratory • Pacific Northwest National Laboratory 	<p>Educational</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alaska Native Science & Engineering Program (ANSEP) • Alaska Pacific University • Alaska Resource Education • Anchorage School District • Kenai Peninsula School District • University of Alaska 	<p>Labor Unions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alaska AFL-CIO • Carpenters Local Union 1243 • Carpenters Local Union 1281 • Cement Masons & Plasterers Local 528 • IBEW Local 1547 • Laborers Union Local 341 • Laborers Union Local 942 • Piledrivers & Divers Local 2520 • Plumbers & Pipefitters UA Local 375 • Public Employees Local 71 • Teamsters Local 959 • United Food and Commercial Workers 	<p>Community & Non-Gov. Organizations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anchorage Economic Development Corp. • Alaska Public Interest Research Group • Alaska Sea Grant • Center for Biological Diversity • Commonwealth North • Cook Inlet Harbor Safety Committee • Cook Inlet Keeper • Cook Inlet Regional Citizens Advisory Council (CIRCAC) • Kenai Peninsula Economic Development District • Kenai Peninsula Fishermen's Association • Natural Resources Defense Council (NRDC) • Renewable Energy Alaska Project (REAP) • Resource Development Council (RDC) • Sierra Club • Upper Cook Inlet Drift Association

Figure 6: Stakeholders for consideration in the permitting process (alphabetical, not exhaustive).

6.2 Collaborative Environmental Reviews

As noted previously, Cook Inlet is home to seven species of marine mammals, of which three (beluga whale, Steller sea lion, and northern sea otter) are considered endangered under the ESA. Other marine mammals in the Cook Inlet protected by the MMPA include killer whale, harbor porpoise, harbor seal, and California sea lion. Threats to the local Beluga population – considered the most endangered population in the nation – are likely to be perceived as the most significant potential negative environmental impact for the installation of a tidal device. In addition to marine mammals, subsistence, commercial, and recreational fisheries, and Essential Fish Habitat (EFH) for various species including salmon, sablefish, flounder, rockfish, sole, and cod can be found throughout Cook Inlet. Project reviews and mitigation measures aimed to reduce potential impacts should be developed in partnership with USFWS and NMFS.

Additionally, a Section 106 review, mandated by the NHPA, requires federal agencies to consider the impact of their projects on historic sites. The review process involves identifying potential effects on historic properties and consulting with various stakeholders, including State Historic Preservation Office (SHPO) and tribal preservation officers, the public, and the Advisory Council on Historic Preservation (ACHP). The goal is to assess any adverse effects and find ways to avoid, minimize, or mitigate them. This may result in a Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) or a Programmatic Agreement (PA), which are legally binding documents that record the outcome of the consultation and ensure compliance with Section 106. The process not only protects the historical integrity of sites but also allows the public to have a say in the preservation of their cultural heritage. Section 106 is triggered in Cook Inlet, or any other location, when a project involves a federal action, such as funding, licensing, or permitting, that has the potential to affect properties listed in or eligible for the National Register of Historic Places.

Ongoing informal and formal consultations with NMFS, USFWS, ADFG, SHPO, and tribal preservation offices will be required to identify and develop effective mitigation, monitoring, and reporting strategies for any tidal energy

development. Given the cost, logistics, and time associated with these types of efforts, a collaborative and proactive state-funded review could significantly reduce the time and fiduciary burden on individual developers.

6.3 Adaptive Management

It is the authors' opinion that the collection of extensive baseline environmental data prior to the installation of a tidal device is unlikely to be effective in reducing environmental impacts. Most environmental monitoring data can vary by location, season, year, or even in some cases, by day, making the future correlations with a tidal device's impact nearly impossible. Alternatively, adaptive management is a systematic and iterative process designed to enable robust decision-making in the face of uncertainty.

Figure 7: Adaptive Management Cycle

Adaptive management is a structured approach that monitors and responds to a device's impact in real-time balancing the need for immediate action with the goal of long-term sustainability. See Figure 7 for a basic workflow diagram. Its goal is to reduce uncertainty through ongoing strategic monitoring and adjusting operational strategies based on outcomes. This approach enhances long-term management by adapting to new information and changing conditions, making it particularly useful in environmental management and conservation. Establishing adaptive management plans alongside monitoring plans allows developers to adjust protocols as results are obtained without having to change the language in the permit, authorization, or license. This dynamic process uses the best available science to inform actions, monitor outcomes, and adjust strategies. It requires flexibility and a willingness by regulatory agencies and stakeholders to change course as new information emerges. By fostering a culture of learning and adaptation, agencies can better respond to changing conditions and improve system resilience. Incorporating adaptive management practices into permitting efforts for tidal energy projects is likely to reduce environmental impact, cost, and the time to commercialization.

6.4 Programmatic NEPA Review

A Programmatic Environmental Assessment (PEA) or Programmatic Environmental Impact Statement (PEIS) can precede any site- or project-specific decisions, providing information and analyses that can be referenced in future NEPA reviews. In theory, this approach could allow federal agencies to review the common components of tidal development, enabling individual developers to focus their tiered NEPA review on unique aspects of their projects. Tiering a NEPA helps streamline and expedite the preparation of the project-specific NEPA reviews. An approved Programmatic NEPA Review could be effective in the long-term if widespread development was anticipated for 10+ developers. However, in the short term it is the authors' opinion that the use of a Programmatic NEPA Review has the potential to stall, or unnecessarily complicate, initial technology demonstrations in Cook Inlet. Programmatic NEPA Reviews can be expensive, time-intensive, and must be triggered by a proposed Federal action such as (1) adopting official federal policy; (2) adopting formal federal plans; (3) adopting federal agency programs; and/or (4) approving multiple federal actions. Because much of the tidal resource and proposed development in Cook Inlet is

within State waters, a collaborative and mutually beneficial strategy for the use of a Programmatic Review under NEPA would need to be coordinated with the Federal Government.

6.5 State-Funded Assessment

As an alternative to a formal Programmatic NEPA Review, a state-funded evaluation similar to the *Cook Inlet Areawide Oil and Gas Lease Sale Best Interest Findings*²² could be used to gather and process existing information related to tidal development in Cook Inlet. This published document could serve as a repository for Cook Inlet data and serve as an easily accessible resource for developers during their individual NEPA evaluations.

As part of the State-Funded Assessment, additional funding to create and maintain robust data collection, monitoring, and stakeholder engagement efforts could further streamline future permitting efforts. Geographic data collection to support archeological/cultural assessments and coordination with NMFS, USFWS, and ADFG could significantly ease the permitting burden on individual developers. Any state-funded data collection should build on existing industry research. Notably, the OES *State of the Science Report*²³ is a comprehensive document summarizing current information from around the globe regarding the environmental effects of marine renewable energy (MRE) development. It provides an update on the interactions between MRE devices, the marine environment, and the wildlife that inhabits it. The report is part of an ongoing effort to support responsible and sustainable MRE development and is used by researchers, policymakers, and industry stakeholders to inform decisions and monitoring strategies. When supplemented with site-specific information, this report can help streamline the installation of tidal energy devices in Cook Inlet.

6.6 Contracts for Difference

Contracts for Difference (CfDs) are increasingly seen as the method of choice for incentivizing investment in clean energy technologies. Available in the UK, CfDs provide a guaranteed sale price, generally above market value, for certain forms of low carbon electricity delivery, including from tidal energy. In each Allocation Round (AR), a maximum “strike” price is provided and qualified applicants proposing to produce renewable energy competitively bid for the final “clearing” price below the strike price. At present, tidal energy in the UK has a dedicated portion of the total AR budget, known as “ringfenced” funding – in 2024 this was £15M dedicated to tidal energy allocations. These financial contracts provide revenue stability to low-carbon energy projects by paying the difference between the market price and a pre-agreed strike price. If the market price is lower than the pre-agreed price, the government pays the project developer the difference; if higher, the developer pays back the excess. To date, nearly 100 MW of tidal energy have been awarded a CfD for energy delivery and this guaranteed revenue stream is a critical driver of tidal energy project development in the UK. In AR4, the clearing price was 178.54 £/MWh (2012 prices) while in AR5 the clearing price was 198 £/MWh (2012 prices). Adjusted for inflation and converted to US dollars, these values are approximately \$312/MWh and \$346/MWh in 2023. The results for AR6 should be released in 4Q 2024.

6.7 Phase Large-Scale Projects

To increase the likelihood of regulatory approval and stakeholder support, the developers of tidal energy projects should consider the phased build-out of technology to reach the proposed installed capacity in a stepwise manner from a relatively small scale to the full project scale. The size and number of phases will be dependent on the proposed total installed capacity. Multiple examples, either proposed or approved, can be seen globally, and are summarized below.

6.7.1 Roosevelt Island Tidal Energy Project (RITE), New York²⁴

Using the FERC Pilot Project License process, Verdant Power received the first FERC license for tidal energy in the

²² <https://dog.dnr.alaska.gov/LeaseSale/SaleArea/Cook%20Inlet> [Accessed 8/2023]

²³ Copping, A.E. and Hemery, L.G., editors. 2020. OES-Environmental 2020 State of the Science Report: Environmental Effects of Marine Renewable Energy Development Around the World. Report for Ocean Energy Systems (OES). doi:10.2172/1632878

²⁴ <https://www.verdantpower.com/rite/> [Accessed 8/2023]

United States in 2012 for the RITE Project located in the East Channel, East River, New York, NY. The total project installed capacity as approved was 1.05 MW with three unique phases proposed: Phase 1 included 105 kW total installed capacity (10% of project capacity); Phase 2 included 420 kW total installed capacity (40% of project capacity); Phase 3 included 1.05 MW total installed capacity (100% of project capacity). Environmental monitoring protocols were designed for each phase and an adaptive management framework was used during the project lifetime. The project was decommissioned in 2021 following the successful completion of Phase 1. This project went on to obtain a full FERC license delivering more than 350 MWh of tidal energy to the utility grid. Additional information is available via the FERC Docket using FERC No. P-12611.

6.7.2 MeyGen Project, Scotland, UK²⁵

MeyGen received approval from The Crown Estate for the MeyGen tidal energy project between the northern coast of Scotland and the Island of Stroma, in the United Kingdom in 2010. The total project installed capacity as approved is 398 MW with four unique phases proposed: Phase 1 includes 6 MW total installed capacity (1.5% of project capacity); Phase 2 includes 34 MW total installed capacity (8.5% of project capacity); Phase 3 includes 86 MW total installed capacity (21.6% of project capacity); Phase 4 includes 398 MW total installed capacity (100% of project capacity). Phase 1 is currently operating and consenting is complete through Phase 3. Phase 4 is currently in planning. More than 50 GWh of energy has been delivered to the utility grid. This project has been further supported by the CfD revenue mechanism available in the UK.

6.7.3 East Foreland Tidal Energy Project, Alaska, USA²⁶

ORPC submitted a Preliminary Permit Application to the FERC in April 2021 for the East Foreland Tidal Energy Project offshore of the East Foreland in the Upper Cook Inlet, Alaska, US. The FERC issued the Preliminary Permit on July 26, 2021. The application proposes an initial 5 MW pilot project (5% of proposed project capacity) with outcomes and results supporting the planning of a phased build-out of up to 100 MW (100% of proposed project capacity). Additional information is available via the FERC Docket using FERC No. P-15116. Prior work is also available under preliminary permits FERC No. P-12679 and FERC No. P-13821.

DOE-Funded Tidal Energy Demonstration

In May 2023, DOE's Water Power Technologies Office (WPTO) released the first large-scale investment (\$35 million) opportunity for a tidal energy research, development, and demonstration site in the United States, DE-FOA-0002845, Topic Area 1. ORPC's East Foreland Tidal Energy Project, dubbed the "American Tidal Energy Project" (ATEP) was selected as one of two marine energy projects²⁷ to receive the first phase of funding for a combined \$6 million.

The first year of this DOE award is competitive. These two projects will evaluate their proposed sites and create plans for licensing, environmental monitoring, site health and safety, site commercialization, stakeholder engagement, community benefits, supply chain procurement, and technology selection and qualification. This phase will culminate in the projects submitting the necessary license and/or permit applications to regulators. At the conclusion of the first phase, DOE will select one project to proceed through the remaining four phases and receive up to an additional \$29 million, concluding with testing and operation of the tidal energy device(s). This award is a significant achievement for ORPC and represents an important opportunity for Alaska to promote its position as a leader in renewable energy.

6.8 Rochdale Envelope Model

An alternative approach to conducting environmental impact assessments is the Rochdale Envelope model. "The adoption of the Rochdale Envelope approach allows a meaningful [Environmental Impact Assessment] EIA to take

²⁵ <https://saerenewables.com/tidal-stream/meygen/> [Accessed 8/2023]

²⁶ <https://elibrary.ferc.gov/eLibrary/search> [Accessed 8/2023; Search P-15116 from 1/1/21 – 8/1/23]

²⁷ <https://www.opalco.com/quick-fact-opalco-tidal-energy-pilot-project/2022/11/>

place by defining a ‘realistic worst case’ scenario that decision makers can consider in determining the acceptability, or otherwise, of the environmental impacts of a project. As long as a project’s technical and engineering parameters fall within the limits of the envelope and the EIA process has considered the impacts of that envelope and provides robust and justifiable conclusions, then flexibility within those parameters is deemed to be permissible within the terms of any consent granted, i.e., if consent is granted on the assessed maximum parameters of a development, any parameters equal to or less than those assessed is permitted to be constructed.”²⁸ While this approach originated from the land-based construction industry in the UK, it has been successfully applied for the consenting of both on-shore and off-shore wind farms and it is now being applied in the consenting of marine energy projects within UK waters.

In particular, the Morlais Project, in northwest Wales, under development by Menter Môn, utilized the Rochdale Envelope approach to secure consent in December 2021 for a 240 MW tidal energy project. The project is sub-divided into eight berths and each berth is preauthorized for a technology archetype (bottom-mounted only; surface-mounted only; bottom-mounted or surface-mounted) while remaining technology developer- (aka device) agnostic. As a part of the consenting process, from the Morlais Project Environmental Statement (ES), Chapter 4: Project Description, Volume I, Oct. 2019, “Dependent on the type of tidal device, full deployment to 240 MW could comprise up to a maximum of 6201 tidal devices, supporting up to 1,648 TECs and up to 740 inter-array cables within the Maritime Defense Zone (MDZ). This represents the worst-case scenario....” The documentation also states that “A phased approach to deployment of the project may be taken, with scale and timeframe of phasing determined by assessments and consideration of mitigation and management undertaken within the ES.” In the consenting process, the “Morlais Project Draft Marine License Conditions” include more than 50 conditions that require compliance during all stages of the project lifecycle. Details regarding the application of the Rochdale Envelope and the consenting process for the Morlais Project are publicly available online.²⁹ The first surface-mounted tidal energy devices (5.62 MW installed capacity) are expected to be deployed in 2025/2026 with additional devices following in subsequent years.

6.9 DOE R-STEP Program

In August 2023, the DOE launched the Renewable Energy Siting through Technical Engagement and Planning (R-STEP) program³⁰ to support states and local communities plan and evaluate large renewable energy projects. This program supports the creation of new, or the expansion of existing, state-based initiatives to improve renewable energy planning and siting. Five to seven state-based collaboratives are awarded between \$1-\$2 million each. Eligible collaboratives include, but are not limited to, state energy offices, Governor's offices, extension offices, universities, non-governmental organizations, community-based organizations, and other organizations. DOE highly encourages state energy offices (or equivalent state agencies) to participate or lead applications. R-STEP funds could be used to:

- Engage local governments and communities to identify renewable energy siting and planning priorities,
- Hire and subcontract to expand technical capacity and leverage experts in the region or state,
- Develop state-specific resources that could improve siting practices and outcomes for local communities and the renewable energy industry, and
- Conduct training and workshops with local governments to improve technical understanding of renewable energy siting.

The R-STEP Program is a competitive grant opportunity that is expected to open regularly. As announced in March 2024, six state-based collaboratives will receive a combined \$10M as well as technical assistance under Round 1³¹. Round 2 applications were due in June 2024 and are anticipated to be announced this fall.

²⁸ https://marine.gov.scot/sites/default/files/chapter_6_-_the_approach_to_eia.pdf

²⁹ <https://www.morlaisenergy.com>

³⁰ <https://www.energy.gov/eere/renewable-energy-siting-through-technical-engagement-and-planning>

³¹ <https://www.energy.gov/eere/renewable-energy-siting-through-technical-engagement-and-planning>

7 Recommendations

Tidal energy development in Cook Inlet presents a significant opportunity with unique challenges for Alaska. Key recommendations are summarized below.

Table 1: Summary of key recommendations for tidal energy development in Cook Inlet.

Challenge	Recommendations for State of Alaska and/or for developers
Permitting timelines can be long	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Promote and support streamlined permitting processes among all federal, state, and local agencies. ▪ Provide state funding for a Cook Inlet “Best Interest Finding” for Tidal Energy to include data collection, processing, and a repository for archeological/cultural assessments, marine mammals, and fisheries. ▪ Consider establishing a collaborative under R-STEP Program to finance portions of Alaska’s renewable goals.
Costs to developers can be significant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Provide matching funds for DOE and other federal awards and investments in technology Research, Development, Demonstration, and Deployment relevant to marine energy. ▪ Provide state funding to create and support a unified stakeholder outreach program for tidal energy. ▪ Host and maintain a database of relevant stakeholders and agencies through state-funding.
Tidal energy installations can cross regulatory boundaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Establish a single division within the Alaska Department of Natural Resources to review and authorize renewable energy projects. ▪ Ensure planning efforts and stakeholder outreach consider the potential impact of project development in federal waters.
Potential impact to endangered species, essential fish habitat, and/or other environmental, historical, recreational, and commercial uses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Provide state funding to develop and implement a proactive, comprehensive strategy for evaluating and responding to potential risks to fisheries, marine mammals, and/or other environmental, historical, recreational, and commercial uses to attract and promote tidal energy development in Cook Inlet. ▪ Use IEA-OES State of the Science reports, and other scientific literature, to inform and educate regulatory agencies and stakeholders.
Monitoring requirements can be significant and costly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Avoid pursuing multi-year baseline environmental monitoring efforts. Instead, implement adaptive management practices with clear pathways to reductions in monitoring once risks are retired or evidence suggests impacts are minimal. ▪ Establish state permitting policies to promote monitoring requirements proportional to the risk (deployment size, rotation rate, etc.) and appropriate for the flow scale (micro, meso, macro) of interest.
Reporting requirements can be significant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Establish a common reporting template and timelines for state agencies and promote continuity of these templates and timelines among federal and local agencies. ▪ Establish agency reporting frequency requirements proportional to the project size and/or risk.